

Re-emphasizing Children's Literature in Second Language Classrooms of Elementary Schools

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ABSTRACT

Language is the means of communications. Language acquisition requires four basic skills namely: listening, speaking, reading and writing. Reading plays a great role in acquiring language. It not only enables the student to gain knowledge but it also helps the student to learn the language, style and vocabulary of the writing. In India only the text books serves the role of a good reading material to arouse the interest of reading books among the students as reading for pleasure is not very common among them. Here the idea of introducing Children's literature is truly remarkable. Children's literature would include reading material written especially for children and in which children are often protagonists. It covers a whole range from alphabet and number books to novels and encyclopedias published for teenagers or young adults. This paper is going to discuss about the role of extra reading materials in enhancing basic linguistic skills among elementary school children of West Bengal.

Introduction

Abraham Lincoln believed that the ideas in reading materials have powerful effects. The National Curriculum Framework (NCF)-2005 states that reading has to be readily accepted as the focus area of language education. The present school syllabi are burdened with information-absorbing and memorizing tasks, so much that the pleasure of reading for its own sake is ignored. Opportunities for individualized reading need to be built at all stages in order to promote a culture of reading, and teachers must set example of being members of such a culture .the development and supply of a range of supplementary reading materials relevant to all school

subjects and across the grades require urgent attention. A great deal of such materials could be utilized in a methodical manner to expand the scope of classroom teaching. The National Curriculum Framework (NCF)-2005 appreciates the importance of a print-rich environment as one of the strongest tools for reading. A word picture or cartoon, printed material in any form definitely motivates the child to see something or to read it. Through the word of books and newspaper he keeps on developing his general knowledge. It is equally essential to highlight an autonomous image of the child in children's literature, which takes into account the child's voice, thoughts, imagination and critical ability. This would enable children's literature to depict inherent values such as the child's ability to take independent decisions, think rationally, logically, etc.

Engaging children with picture books with the purpose to enhance their linguistic expressions is considered to be a fruitful activity. Such activities also facilitate them in exploring their visual experiences. Picture books have enjoyed immense popularity in the classroom over the past few decades within the school system. They have been meaningfully used in classrooms to develop story writing, reading comprehension, and oral language skill and vocabulary recognition. It can also increase listening comprehension, retelling, and grammatical awareness etc in students of all ages. Many experts in the field of literacy have acknowledged the comic to be a wonderful tool to engage the reluctant readers and teaching literacy themes. In Graphic Novels as educational heavyweights, Jonathan Seyfried, describe the current trend of losing readers to electronic gadgets. With the bright colors and familiar characters, comics are more appealing than traditional text. The comic represents something different and exciting without sacrificing plot vocabulary, and other important components of reading comprehension. For these reason and many more, comics might also play an important role in English Language Learners (ELLs) acquisition of language.

In Indian families, parents are heard warning their children not to waste their time reading materials other than their textbooks. However as a nation we also love to complain about the death of the reading habit. The implication, of course, is that reading fiction or literature is a waste of time. But it is also an acknowledgement of the power of a good book to draw us in. The books they read to gain pleasure have certainly had a great impact on their language acquisition. In most Indian schools the text book continues to be the voice of authority and often the only text available for reading inside classrooms. The language classroom also treats the text book

as content that needs to be ‘covered’ during one academic year, than as a compilation of children’s reading materials offering possibilities of interpretation.

Given this context, it is imperative for teacher education programs in India to offer a course in children’s literature. One such program is the four-year Bachelor’s in Elementary Education (B. El. Ed) degree offered by the University of Delhi. In the second year student teachers read , discuss and analyze children’s literature in order to see its connection with literacy and reading for pleasure. In the third and fourth year, when student teachers intern in schools they discover the power of using good children’s literature to enable the students in their elementary classrooms to become readers, writers and critical thinkers.

Review of related literature

Zsuzsanna, K. (2017) has conducted a study entitled ‘the possible benefits of using comic books in foreign language education: a classroom study’. This study aimed at investigating some of these (guessing, meaning of new words, lowered anxiety, better recall) by the use of comic books in the classroom. In this study researcher recruited three groups of students in a secondary grammar school as part of the researcher’s 11-week-long formal English teaching practice. .The findings of the study reveal some tendencies in the data that point toward the benefits of using comic books might have in foreign language education. Therefore, in cases where technological demands are left unsolved, the application of comic books in foreign language learning and home assignments are recommended instead of in-class use in education.

Madani, H. (2016) has conducted a study titled ‘The effects of reading skills on the development of language proficiency’. This study focus on the impact of reading on the development of students’ language learning. The aim of this study is to illustrate the roles of the reading skills in enhancing the English language proficiency. It attempts to clarify how reading can be used to improve the language skills including writing, speaking, listening, vocabulary, and grammar. The results are that both classroom and extensive reading have abundant language learning benefits. Moreover, the results showed that the lack of motivation and language competence are the main obstacles that cause poor reading. This put great challenges and demands on teachers as they are required to use effective classroom strategies, provide adequate reading instruction to first year EFL students, and set extensive reading programs.

Adhikary, S. R. (2015) has conducted a study entitled, 'Impact of Japanese cartoons on primary school going children: with special reference to Doraemon.' The paper focuses on the children's understanding of these Japanese cartoons they watch and the cause for which they fanatically attached to their characters. In this study researcher closely identified and analyzed various child psychology aspects such as cognition, emotion and gratification, which children are endowed with through these programs. The researcher examined the popularity of Doraemon in particular, Vis a Vis other cartoons programs. This study has revealed the fact that with the localization of series of foreign cartoons show the popularity of cartoons has multiplied. Among all Japanese cartoons are leading and the most popular show is Doraemon. Researcher find their change in behavior, perception and attitude under the influence of these programs must be closely monitored and rectified whenever and however required.

Govender, R. (Feb., 2015) has conducted a study entitled 'Factors that affect foundation phase English second language learners' reading and writing skills'. This study focus on the factors that affect foundation phase English second language learners' reading and writing skills. Researcher conducted this mix-method study at five English medium primary schools in Port Shepstone. It was found that the learners' home language background significantly affected their pronunciation of words in English, their ability to use phonics to read and write, and their ability to differentiate between male & female when writing sentences. Overall from this study researcher revealed that the English language has significantly impacted on all aspects of the isiZulu-speaking foundation phase learners' lives, and more especially has considerably influenced their reading and writing achievements at English medium schools.

Wanzek, J., Roberts, g., Otaiba, S. A., Kent, S. C., (2014) has conducted a study entitled 'The relationship of print reading in tier 1 instruction and reading achievement for kindergarten students at risk of reading difficulties'. The purpose of this study is to examine the amount of time kindergarten students at risk of reading difficulties actively engaged in reading print during Tier I reading instruction, and the extent to which time in reading print was related to end-of-year reading achievement. Findings revealed the amount of time students were engaged in reading print predicted end-of-year reading achievement, although time engaged in reading print during Tier I was limited overall. Student- and teacher-level factors and their relationship to the amount of time students engage in reading print is also examined.

Lucht, M. & Heidig, S. (Oct 2013), has conducted a study entitled ‘Applying HOPSCOTCH as an extra-learning game in English lesson’. Researcher conducted two exploratory studies at a German elementary school and investigated the potential of HOPSCOTCH to engage students, as well as to facilitate the acquisition of factual knowledge (English vocabulary) and to improve the attitudes of students towards learning English as a second language. The results of these studies indicated that the students remembered and correctly spelled about the same number of new vocabulary words after learning with HOPSCOTCH as they did after a teacher-centered lesson. As such we suggest that exer-learning games could serve as additional class room control and teaching aids in school.

Merc, A. (January 2013) has conducted a study Entitled, ‘The effect of comic strips on EFL reading comprehension’. This study focus on the effects of Comic Strips on reading comprehension of Turkish EFL learners. In this study researcher divided 167 university student from two proficiency levels (lower-intermediate and upper-intermediate) into four treatment groups – low level text only , low level text with Comic Strips, high level text only and high level text with Comic Strips. Students read the given texts and wrote on a separated answer sheet what they remembered about the text. Researcher analyzed the collected data through scoring the Immediate Recall Protocols (IRP). As a result of the research all students with a Comic Strips effect regardless of proficiency and text level, performed better than the ones without the Comic Strips. The researcher through this study was confirmed that tDual Coding Theory (DCT) on the account that students are better at comprehending reading texts that are accompanied with visual.

Baker. A. (May 2011) has conducted a study entitled, ‘Using comics to improve literacy in English language learners’ The purpose of this study is to examine the benefits of using comics with English Language Learners (ELLs). Many experts in the field of literacy have acknowledged the comic to be a wonderful tool to engage the reluctant reader and to have important literary benefits, such as attracting reluctant readers and teaching literary themes. The findings of the study suggest that comics not only attract reluctant readers, but they are being used to teach advanced themes in literature and visual literacy. With their bright colors and popular characters, comics are more appealing than traditional texts without sacrificing plot or vocabulary.

Dissa, S. & Lim (June 2010) has conducted a study entitled, 'Exploring the use of picture books in developing the language English as a second language.' The aim of this study is to explore what research says about the effectiveness of using picture books to support language acquisition among students learning English as a second language. In this study researcher grouped the research into the following themes: book floods, the effect of using picture books on a specific ability or skill and wordless picture books. Flooded communities researcher in the south pacific and China with high interest western picture books and examined the effect that those picture books had on different learning outcomes related to story structure, oral language and reading comprehension and they were exposed to picture books showed significant improvement in oral language, comprehension and use of story structure elements. Other experimental research wanted to compare the effects of a book based program as opposed to the use of an audio-lingual highly structured textbooks and there were found that there was a significant increase in language comprehension, vocabulary and expression when using picture books. Lastly some of the research revolved around case studies or experimental studies on how wordless books can be used to promote language learning and there were also found to be an excellent resource for facilitating language development in students learning English as a second language. In this study researcher used the different picture book versions of the '3 Little Pigs' for students to participate in activities designed to enhance their language acquisition.

Knowledge gap

By the observing above mentioned studies researcher found that few studies were conducted on impact of extra reading materials on language development among children of elementary school, secondary school but there may be no or less study were conducted on impact of extra reading materials on language development among elementary school children in context of West Bengal. Thus researcher found here a knowledge gap in the field of research on impact of extra reading materials on language development of elementary school children as they are the future destiny makers of our nation.

Rationale of the study

The impact of extra reading materials on language development of the elementary children is huge and universally accepted. It not only enables the students to gain knowledge but also helps the students to gain

knowledge but also helps the student to learn the language, style and vocabulary of the writing. According to the researcher's views, reading plays a great role in acquiring language. However, extra reading materials in the form of children's literature along with the text books surely help the student to develop their language acquisitions skills more proficiently. The only material available in classes is the text books. Learning to gain language development requires the support of materials like extra books, comic books, etc. This side should be taken care of by the school authority.

Operational definition of the terms used

Extra Reading Materials: It is readily available in the form of comprehensible input i.e. other than school textbooks, especially helpful for students in learning target language or second language. If carefully chosen to suit learners' level, it offers them repeated encounters with language items they have already met. This helps in developing learners' autonomy to communicate in second language. These are may be in the form of story books, comics, cartoon strips, biographies, etc.

Language Learning: Language learning refers to the process by which humans acquire the capacity to perceive and comprehend language, as well as to produce and use words and sentences to communicate. This process is an active process which begins at birth and continues throughout life. Students learn language as they use it to communicate their thoughts, feelings, and experiences, establish relationships with family members and strive to make sense and order of their world.

Reading Comprehension: Comprehension is a complex cognitive process in which a reader intentionally and interactively engages with the text. It heavily depends on skilled word recognition and decoding, oral reading fluency, well-developed vocabulary and active engagement with the text.

Vocabulary Development: Vocabulary development is the process by which a person increasing the number of words which he or she uses in everyday life. It is a critical aspect of reading comprehension. Peoples continue to develop vocabulary throughout their lives.

Elementary School: Elementary school is a school for students in their first school years, where they get primary education before they enter secondary education. The exact ages vary by country. In India, elementary schools provide education from class 1 to class 8 with pupils aged between 6 and 15 years old.

Research Questions

1. How extra reading materials influence the second language learning among elementary students?
2. What are the problems being faced by learners in elementary grade in their second language learning?
3. How extra reading materials can help in improving the second language among elementary students?
4. How extra reading materials help in developing vocabulary and reading comprehension among students?
5. How extra reading materials can help in joyful learning?

Objectives of the study

1. To find out the types of extra reading materials in enhancing second language among learners.
2. To know how extra reading materials enhance the reading comprehension among learner.
3. To know how extra reading materials enhance the vocabulary among learners.
4. To study how extra reading materials can produce humor among learners.

Methodology

This study was designed to adopt the descriptive survey method to understand the recent trends going on in language classrooms, for prioritizing children's literature and read for pleasure texts as well. Though the different age groups of children, now-a-days are spontaneously taking part in language and literacy practices other than the schools' text sources, popular culture has entered in the language classrooms in one or other ways. Birbhum was selected as the population of the study, one of the districts of West Bengal having its own history of Folk literature (*baul*) and Rabindranath Tagore's legacy of Children's literature. Eighty Bengali speaking students were selected from three Government schools of Bolpur, Birbhum. For collection of data the researcher prepared some self made questionnaire on extra reading texts, after conducting a pilot study for understanding the nature, types and content of extra reading texts. With expert opinions and following the process of standardization the researcher has selected the texts of *Handa-Bhonda*' comics, *Nonte-Fonte* comics, *Chota-Bheem* cartoons, *Motu-Patlu* cartoons and *Tom & Jerry* cartoons for testing English vocabulary and reading comprehension skills of elementary

students. Lastly a content analysis was done of the concerned texts for analyzing the humor producing aspects of the extra reading texts and their impact on raising the reading comprehension and second language reading skill among students.

Findings of the study

The study suggested that reading comprehension, vocabulary development and humorous learning is directly related to extra reading materials. Extra reading materials which draw upon students' backgrounds are desirable. Both comprehension and engagement are enhanced when students can activate relevant background knowledge as they read,

1. Vocabulary development is directly related to extra reading materials. Learning a second language is more effective when it happens in authentic language stimuli that are understandable and attractive. With this type of reading materials students get complete picture of the use of new words in their natural environment.
2. Comics, cartoons, picture books etc, these types of extra reading materials stimulate learner's power of imagination that can be reflected in written or spoken discourses. When students write a response or an essay about a comics or cartoon, they tend to employ vocabulary they get from those materials into a meaningful writing tasks in which the comics or cartoons are the main focus. They respond by imagining situations and characters that reflect their own view towards a social context. In addition, comics, picture books & cartoon creations enhance students to imagine and write character's speeches.
3. While reading the comic strips, cartoons & picture books, student observe the character's speech, word selection, tenses used, jokes used and general appearance of the characters. When tackling the comics, cartoons and picture books, students compare and connect to their existing experiences of a same subject matter, and then they evaluate their understanding in a group work.
4. Extra reading materials can probably enhance interactive teaching and learning practices in language classroom that both have significant pedagogical values towards language performance and learner's personal skills.
5. Comic strips like Tintin, Batul the Great, Nonte-Fonte & cartoons like Chota Bheem, Motu-Patlu represent everyday life experiences. Students can easily evaluate their skill of reconceptualising previous

knowledge and that they share with peers. Those comics and cartoons enable students to employ vocabulary they gain from comics & cartoons in collaborative discussions and accomplish learning task based on that comics & cartoons.

6. According to this survey it was found that Tintin, Batul the Great, Nonte-Fonte & Handa-Bhonda are very popular comic strips and Chota Bheem & Motu-Patlu are the most popular cartoons played an important role in having proficiency as well as competencies in second language

Conclusion

The impact of extra of reading materials is an important aspect in the life of students that promotes their cognitive functioning and develops the language skills efficiently. Extra reading materials play a very vital role among the students in acquiring language development. The National Curriculum Framework (NCF)-2005 states that reading has to be readily accepted as the focus area of language education. Language acquisition requires continuous practice development and refinement and here the extra reading materials with its creativity and interesting ideas plays a very crucial role. Thus the impact of extra reading materials among the elementary school children is benevolent. The main objectives of the extra reading materials like comic strips, cartoons, short story, picture books personify the childhood days as the children gets an impression of their own characters from those extra reading materials. They can relate themselves with it. So their learning will be interesting. Comic strips, cartoons, short story, picture books can help us to design constructive learning and to develop them in future. In our second language classroom we can apply a new approach by breaking the traditional lesson plan. If we use comic strips, cartoons, short story, picture books, these types of extra reading materials in language classroom it will help to develop an equity pedagogy. Where equity pedagogy means all the students are treated equally, there should be no biasness. Besides it will help to promote the cultural pedagogy in any way.

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